

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the ninth regular issue of 2023. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and our editorial board and guest reviewers for the extremely valuable reviews and suggestions for improvement. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, enable us to run our journal successfully and maintain its quality.

Still, I would like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and emerging trends.

As we want to secure the financial support also for the years to come, we are looking for institutions and libraries to financially support our diamond open access journal as consortium members, who will then benefit from the research community, international visibility, and the opportunity to manage special issues and focused topics within the journal. Please think about the possibility of such financial participation by your institution, we would be very grateful for any kind of support.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce five accepted papers involving 22 authors from 10 different countries: Austria, Brazil, Estonia, France, Lebanon, Malaysia, Spain, The Netherlands, United Kingdom, and Vietnam.

In a collaborative research effort, Jan Bergstra from The Netherlands and John V. Tucker from the United Kingdom introduce the Naive Fracterm Calculus, which is a new perspective on elementary arithmetic and can be described as naive when compared to a variety of algebraic and logical, axiomatic formalisations of elementary arithmetic. Ricardo Caceffo, Jacques Wainer, Guilherme Gama, Islene Garcia, and Rodolfo Azevedo from Brazil conducted a study based on perceptual learning modules, more specifically a variation of perceptual learning based on multiple-choice questionnaires to be used in an introductory programming course, and report on related issues. In a collaborative research work between colleagues from Malaysia, Lebanon and France, Mohammad Kchouri, Norharyati Harum, Hussein Hazimeh, and Ali Obeid suggest a new technique to detect falls by combining Fuzzy Logic and Support Vector Machine, achieving an overall accuracy of about 99.87% in detecting the fall function. In an international research collaboration between Estonia, Austria, Spain, Luis P. Prieto, Gerti Pishtari, Yannis Dimitriadis, María Jesús Rodríguez-Triana, Tobias Ley, and Paula Odriozola-González propose and explore single-case learning analytics, which defines a process in which doctoral students, researchers, and computational elements collaborate to extract insights into a single learner's experience and learning process. Last but not least, also in a joint research work by researchers

from Vietnam and the United Kingdom, Nguyen Van Hieu, Ngo Le Huy Hien, Luu Van Huy, Nguyen Huy Tuong, and Pham Thi Kim Thoa present their approach PlantKViT for forest plants classification, which is based on a combination model of Vision Transformer and KNN and achieves a 93% accuracy.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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